

NANOCOMPOSITE FIBRILS FROM GRAPHITE NANOPLATELETS

Lisa Viculis,¹ Julia Mack,¹ Ashraf Ali,² Russell Luoh,¹ Guoliang Yang,² Richard Kaner,¹
Thomas Hahn,¹ and Frank Ko^{2*}

1. *University of California, Los Angeles, CA 90095*

2. *Drexel University, Philadelphia, PA, 19104*

ABSTRACT

This paper introduces a new reinforcement form for nanocomposites. Graphite nanoplatelets are produced by a chemical route using a low energy intercalation/exfoliation process providing an alternative, low cost pathway to nanomaterials. In this process, graphite is heated to 200 °C in the presence of potassium to form the first stage intercalation compound, KC_8 . Exfoliation in ethanol then creates a dispersion of graphitic sheets. In a previous study, it has been shown that single-walled carbon nanotubes (SWNT) can be dispersed in polymer solutions to form nanocomposite fibrils by the electrospinning process. In order to achieve orientation and to facilitate processing and assessment of the engineering properties of the nanosheets, the graphite nanoplatelets were dispersed in a 7 wt. % polyacrylonitrile (PAN) solution in N,N Dimethylformamide (DMF) to form nanoscale fibrils by the electrospinning process. The composite fibrils were characterized by Thermogravimetric Analysis (TGA), Scanning Electronic Microscopy (SEM), Transmission Electron Microscopy (TEM), and Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) for samples consisting of 1-4 wt. % of graphite nanoplatelets (GNP).

Keywords: graphite nanoplatelet, intercalation, exfoliation, nanocomposite fibril, electrospinning

BACKGROUND

In recent years, polymer layered silicate nanocomposites have attracted increased attention due to their potential to significantly enhance the mechanical properties, thermal stability, flame retardancy, and barrier properties, etc. of the polymer with only a small addition of (less than 4 % by volume) the nano-clay [1-8]. This is attributed to the large aspect ratio and the availability of enormous surface area [9]. In this study, we investigate the feasibility of the formation of graphite nanoplatelets (GNP) by an intercalation/exfoliation process and subsequently incorporating the GNP into a nanocomposite fibril by the electrospinning process.

Graphite consists of one atom thick layers of carbon, separated by a van der Waals gap of 3.34 Å. By separating the graphitic layers through intercalation and then exfoliation, nanoplatelets can be formed which satisfy the high aspect ratio criteria for high strength composites. In addition to their unique chemistry, graphite is also one of the strongest materials known per unit weight. Thus, their layered morphology coupled with light weight make them ideal as reinforcements for high strength materials. As nanoclays are analogous to glass fiber reinforcements in composites, GNP may potentially play the role of super graphite fibers in nanocomposites.

Graphite nanoplatelets are synthesized using known graphite intercalation chemistry [10]. The starting material is crystalline graphite powder to which potassium is added as an intercalant. Potassium was used instead of the lighter alkali metals, since the ionization energy of lithium (5.39 eV) and sodium (5.14 eV) are higher than the electron affinity of graphite (4.6 eV). Since the ionization energy of potassium (4.34 eV) lies below the electron affinity of graphite, the reaction will

go to completion without the use of high pressures and temperatures, thus facilitating low cost manufacturing.

The formation of GNP/polymer nanocomposites was carried out using the electrospinning process. The electrostatic spinning, or electrospinning, process is a simple and non-mechanical process analogous to electro-spraying developed some sixty years ago [11]. Because of its simplicity and capability of generating nanoscale fibers from polymer solutions and melts under ambient conditions, there has been a revival of interest in the electrospinning process to create structures that have ultra-high surface areas and as a means for the alignment of nanofillers such as layered silicates or nanotubes [12-15].

In the electrospinning process, as illustrated in Figure 1, an electric field is generated between an oppositely charged polymer fluid and a grounded collection screen. A polymer solution is added to a syringe with a needle as the capillary tip. An electrode is placed in the solution with another connection made to a metal collection screen. As the electrical potential is increased, the charged polymer solution is attracted to the screen. Once the voltage reaches a critical value, the charge overcomes the surface tension of the polymer cone formed on the capillary tip of the syringe and a jet of ultrafine fibers with diameters ranging from 5-500 nm are produced. As the charged fibers are sprayed, the solvent quickly evaporates and the fibers are accumulated randomly or laid parallel on the surface of the collection screen. This results in a porous, nonwoven film of nano to micron scale fibers. Fiber diameter and film thickness can be controlled by varying charge density, polymer solution concentration and the duration of electrospinning. In addition, co-electrospinning can be carried out by mixing one or more types of functional nanoparticles, nanoplatelets, or nanotubes during solution preparation, resulting in ultrafine nanocomposite fibers that have a multitude of electronic and structural functionality.

Figure 1. Schematic of the co-electrospinning setup for production of GNP/Polymer nanocomposite fibrils.

PROCESSING OF GNP/PAN NANOCOMPOSITES

Formation of GNP - The first stage intercalation compound, KC_8 , was synthesized by adding a stoichiometric amount of potassium, 81.4 mg (0.0021 moles) to 200 mg (0.0167 moles) of high purity graphite (SP-1 from Bay Carbon, Inc.) in a Pyrex tube capped with a stopcock. All transfers were carried out in a helium filled drybox (< 1 ppm H_2O and O_2). The reactant filled tube was evacuated, sealed and heated for 16 hours at 200 °C. A uniform, bright gold compound formed.

Potassium intercalated graphite is very air sensitive and reacts vigorously with water or alcohols. Pure ethanol was found to be an effective exfoliating agent, as given in equation 1.

The intercalated graphite turns from gold to black as the sheets exfoliate. Bubbling is observed, consistent with hydrogen evolution. The resulting solution is basic due to the formation of potassium ethoxide. The dispersion of graphitic sheets in ethanol was then allowed to settle. The solvent was decanted and the product washed several times with ethanol until a neutral pH was obtained (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Schematic of the intercalation/exfoliation process. Graphite is intercalated with potassium to form the first stage intercalation compound, KC_8 and then exfoliated in aqueous solvents to produce graphite nanoplatelets (GNP).

Co-Electrospinning - In this study, polyacrylonitrile (PAN) (MW ~150,000 from Scientific Polymer Products, Inc., Ontario, NY) solutions were prepared by mixing PAN with N,N Dimethylformamide (DMF) and then sonicated for 20 minutes. Sonication was carried out in 5

minute intervals in order to avoid overheating the solution. A magnetic stirrer was used to uniformly distribute the heat generated during sonication.

The composite solution was prepared by mixing graphite nanoplatelets (GNP) first with DMF. The samples were then sonicated for one hour at 80 W (FS-20 ultrasonic cleaner) in order to disperse the GNP before mixing with PAN. To this dispersion was dissolved 7 wt. % PAN to form the spinning solution following the same procedure outlined before. The amount of GNP added was varied from 1-4 wt. %. Following the process described earlier, an electrostatic field of 20 kV was applied over a distance of 15 cm between the tip of the syringe needle and a 75 mm x 75 mm (3" x 3") aluminum foil covered sample collection ground plate.

STRUCTURE OF GNP/PAN NANOCOMPOSITES

Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was used to observe the particle and fiber size, as well as the degree of dispersion of the GNP within the polymer after electrospinning into fiber form. The samples were dispersed on carbon grids (Ted Pella, Redding, CA) using ethanol and imaged with a JEOL-2000 FX TEM. The background web pattern seen in all the electron micrographs is the lacey carbon grid support. The entire 1-4 wt. % GNP/PAN series was imaged.

Figure 3. Transmission electron micrographs of 4 wt. % GNP/PAN nanofibers. a) Overview showing nanofibers 5-50 nm in diameter, b) a PAN droplet surrounding by 4 wt. % GNP/PAN nanofibers where a GNP has contorted to fit within the fiber diameter. The lighter web pattern in the background is the lacey carbon TEM grid.

Figure 3a shows a TEM image of a representative sample of the 4 wt. % GNP/PAN nanocomposite fibers. The diameters of fibers seen in this transmission electron micrograph range from 5-50 nm. Since a TEM image is the result of projection through a sample, very thin objects are not visible. Hence, the GNP cannot be distinguished in Fig. 3 since they are embedded within the PAN fibers. However, if the thin graphite sheets roll up on themselves, the increased thickness allows them to be visible in TEM. Figure 3b shows a range of nanofiber diameters. The large sphere

is a PAN droplet which is a by-product of the electrospinning process. Wrapping around the polymer droplet are 4 wt. % GNP/PAN fibers with diameters of 50-175 nm. At the top left of the PAN droplet, a brighter object appears embedded within the fiber. This is a graphite nanoplatelet that was too large to fit within the fiber, and hence scrolled onto itself in order to decrease one dimension. The result is these carbon “nanotube-like” structures within the polymer matrix. Given sufficient energy, graphite nanoplatelets have been observed to form scroll-like structures [16].

Figure 4. a) Dark field TEM image of a 1 wt. % GNP/PAN nanofiber and b) selected area electron diffraction pattern of GNP incorporated within PAN nanofiber.

The PAN nanofibers are amorphous, however the graphite nanoplatelets should show some degree of crystallinity. Figure 4a is a TEM image of a 1 wt. % GNP/PAN nanofiber observed in dark field mode. The darker spots seen within the fibers are specific crystallographic planes that are being diffracted by the electron beam. Figure 4b is the resulting selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern for that particular nanofiber. A hexagonal polycrystalline spot pattern is observed, consistent with a graphitic crystal structure. Since the polymer fiber is amorphous and a spot pattern is observed, this provides evidence that the GNP are in fact being incorporated into the polymer nanofibers.

Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was also used to examine the particle dispersion within the fibers. This gives an idea of uniformity, the presence of any large aggregates, and the orientation of the platelets. Loose samples were affixed to graphite disks with carbon tape, gold coated (20 Å thickness), and imaged with a Cambridge Stereoscan 250.

Since graphite is a layered material, an inspection of pristine graphite crystals in SEM should reveal a plate-like appearance, but with thicknesses that vary greatly. Once graphite has been intercalated with potassium, and then exfoliated in ethanol to form GNP, a completely different morphology is revealed. Figure 5 shows an SEM image of GNP after removing the residual ethanol solvent. The layers are clearly being separated into an accordion-like structure. The appearance of “kinked” sheets of graphite, as seen in the foreground of Fig. 5 implies that the graphite sheets are

getting thin enough to disrupt their normal planar structure. Since the resolution of SEM is limited, there may be even further fine structure within the thin layers of GNP. Interruption of the c axis of the graphite, while maintaining the same dimensions in the ab plane, allows for a very high aspect ratio to be achieved. The added flexibility of the thin sheets allows for contortion of the sheets to fit within the nanofiber diameters.

Figure 5. Scanning electron micrograph of graphite nanoplatelets showing the expanding “accordion” structure of the layers as a result of the intercalation/exfoliation process.

Figure 6 shows an SEM image of an electrospun mat of 1 wt. % GNP/PAN nanofibers as deposited on the aluminum foil collector screen. Isolated polymer droplets can be seen, along with polymer “bulges” that occur periodically along a fiber axis. The SEM shows a fairly uniform size distribution of nanofiber diameters. Due to the lower resolution of the SEM, GNP embedded within the fibers will not be visible. However, flakes of graphite that were too large to become trapped within the polymer fiber, are entangled within the fiber mat, as can be seen by the large plate in the background of the micrograph.

Figure 6. Scanning electron micrograph of a 1 wt. % GNP/PAN fiber mat as deposited on the aluminum foil collection screen. The larger graphite flake in the center of the image is too large to be incorporated within the diameter of the nanofibers.

PROPERTIES OF GNP/PAN NANOCOMPOSITES

Thermal Stability - Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) was used to probe how the addition of graphite nanoplatelets within the polymer fibers affects the thermal properties. TGA was also performed on the nanoplatelets themselves to determine stability in air, and compared to crystalline graphite. For each experiment, the analysis was carried out from room temperature to 1000 °C ramped at 5 °C/min in air on a TA Instruments Hi-Res TGA 2950 Thermogravimetric Analyzer. Crystalline graphite is stable in air up to 650 °C, above which point it is completely oxidized to carbon dioxide. The graphite nanoplatelets are stable until 450 °C, about 200 °C less than pure graphite, consistent with nanomaterials.

The entire 1-4 wt. % GNP/PAN nanofiber series was analyzed under the same conditions described above. Thermal analysis revealed two major weight losses as shown in Figure 7. A small amount of weight loss can be detected at less than 100 °C. This is most likely due to removal of residual solvent (DMF or ethanol). For pristine PAN fibers without any GNP present, the first major weight loss occurs at ~300 °C, and the second weight loss appears occurs at ~ 400 °C, consistent with the degradation pattern of PAN [15]. The subsequent addition of increasing percentages of GNP within the PAN fibers shows a change in thermal degradation pattern with an increase in thermal stability with increasing wt. % of GNP. For example, at 50 % weight loss, an increase in thermal stability of 25 °C is observed for the 4 wt. % GNP/PAN composite. The general trend shows an increase in thermal stability with increasing percentages of GNP incorporated within the PAN fibers. Some fluctuations in this trend are observed at temperatures above 500 °C due to inhomogeneities of the nanofiber composites.

Figure 7. Thermogravimetric analysis in air of pristine PAN and 1-4 wt. % GNP/PAN nanofiber composites showing increased thermal stability upon addition of increasing wt. % GNP.

Mechanical Properties - Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) was used to measure the mechanical properties of the GNP/PAN fibers. To prepare the specimens for AFM testing, the electrospun composite fibrils were stabilized in an oven at 200 °C for 20 minutes in air. The composite fibril specimens were then fixed on a 5 x 5 mm mica sheet with a drop of PAN/DMF matrix. The fibril/PAN composite specimens were left on the mica overnight to allow the DMF solvent to evaporate.

The fibrils were first imaged, and the AFM tip was then positioned on top of the fiber at the point of interest. Figure 8 shows an AFM image of a PAN/GNP fibril composite specimen.

Figure 8. AFM image of a stabilized electrospun GNP/PAN nanofiber composite.

The elastic modulus of the fiber can be evaluated based on the measured parameters using the approach of Kracke and Damaschke [18]. The method utilizes the relationship $dF/d(\Delta z) = (2/\pi^{1/2})E^*A^{1/2}$, where A is the contact area, E^* is the effective Young's modulus of the contact as defined by: $1/E^* = (1-\nu_1^2)/E_1 + (1-\nu_2^2)/E_2$. Here, E_1 , E_2 and ν_1 and ν_2 are the elastic moduli and the Poisson's ratios of the sample and the tip. A silicon carbide tip of 5 nm radius and 130 GPa elastic modulus was used. Three different measurements were made for each sample with the same magnification on three different locations for each sample. Figure 10 shows the force-deformation curves for a fibril specimen with 3 % by weight of GNP. The mica was used as a standard since its elastic modulus has been determined using the same method [18]. Table 1 provides a summary of the calculated Young's modulus for the GNP/PAN composite fibrils.

The Young's modulus of the GNP/PAN composite fibrils shown in Table 1 were plotted as a function of GNP weight/volume fraction as illustrated in Figure 11. For comparison purposes, a rule of mixture plot was also constructed, assuming a Young's modulus of 1000 GPa for the graphene sheets. It is of interest to note that the experimental results depart significantly from the rule of mixture prediction showing a five-fold increase in volume fraction effect. This may be attributed to the high aspect ratio of the dispersed GNP, which is related to the amount of exfoliated layers.

Figure 10. Force vs. Indentation plot for electrospun 3 wt. % GNP/PAN nanofiber composite.

Table 1. Elastic modulus of 1- 4 wt. % GNP/PAN composite fibrils

GNP wt %	1%	2%	3%	4%
Measurement				
1	89.71	128.14	148.25	153.24
2	71.77	139.78	97.59	123.79
3	70.15	70.15	118.15	123.26
Average (GPa)	77.21	112.69	121.33	133.43
Standard Deviation (GPa)	10.89	37.30	25.48	17.16

CONCLUSIONS

Graphite nanoplatelets (GNP) were fabricated via an intercalation/exfoliation process. The GNP were extruded into a PAN matrix by the electrospinning process to create ultrafine GNP/PAN composite fibrils, thus providing a convenient means for the dispersion of the GNP. With an aspect ratio of over 1000, the GNP provides an efficient means for stress transfer and thus serves as an excellent reinforcement for composites. TEM observations reveal not only the presence of GNP in the PAN fibril matrix, but also shows the formation of scroll-like tubular graphene structures. TGA measurements of the GNP/PAN composite fibrils show a gradual decrease in the rate of thermal degradation by the addition of 4 % by weight or less of GNP. At 50 % weight loss, an increase of the degradation temperature by 25 °C was observed with the introduction of 4 % by weight of GNP. The Young's modulus of the GNP/PAN composite fibrils were measure by AFM. A five-fold increase in reinforcement effect was observed. Based on these encouraging results, further investigations are being carried out with other polymer matrices, as well as the exploration of other functional nanoparticles to be incorporated within the electrospun fibrils.

Figure 11. Young's Modulus of GNP/PAN composite fibrils as a function of GNP volume fraction and weight percent.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was carried out during FK's sabbatical leave at UCLA. The support of the Office of Naval Research and the Air Force Office of Scientific Research is gratefully acknowledged.

REFERENCES:

- Messersmith, P. B., Giannelis, E. P., *Chem. Mater.* **5**, 1064 (1993).
- Kojima, Y., Usuki, A., Kawasumi, M., Okada, A., Fukushima, Y., Kurauchi, T., Kamigaito, O., *J. Mater. Res.* **8**, 1185 (1993).
- Usuki, A., Kojima, Y., Kawasumi, M., Okada, A., Fukushima, Y., Kurauchi, T., Kamigaito, O., *J. Mater. Res.* **8**, 1179 (1993).
- Brown, J. M., Curliss, D., Vaia, R. A., *Chem. Mater.* **12**, 3376 (2000).
- Zilg, C., Thomann, R., Finter, J., Mulhaupt, R., *Macromol. Mater. Eng.* **208/281**, 41 (2000).
- Fu, X., Qutubuddin, S., *Polymer* **42**, 807 (2001).
- Chin, I. -J., Thurn-Albrecht, T., Kim, H. -C., Russell, T. P., Wang, J., *Polymer* **42**, 5947 (2001).
- Alexandre, M., Dubois, P., *Mat. Sci. Eng.* **28**, 1 (2000).
- Schadler, L. S., Giannaris, S. C.; Ajayan, P. M., *App. Phys. Lett.* **73**, 3842 (1998).
- Bartlett, N., McQuillan, B. W. in *Intercalation Chemistry* (eds Whittingham, M. S., Jacobson, A. J.) Academic Press, New York, 1982, pp. 19-53.
- Formhals, A., US Patent 1,975,504, (1934).
- Doshi, J., Reneker, D. H., *J. Electrostatics* **35**, 151 (1995).
- Ko, F. K., Han, W. B., Rahman, Zhou, O., *Proc. Am. Soc. Comp.*, 16th 388 (2001).
- Fong, H., Liu, W., Wang, C. -S, Vaia, R. A, *Polymer* **43**, 775 (2002).
- Ko, F. K., Khan, S., Ali, A., Gogotsi, Y., Naguib, N., Yang, G., Li, C., Shimoda, H., Zhou, O., Bronikowski, M. J., Smalley, R. E., Willis, P. A., AIAA Conference, Denver, Colorado, April 23rd, 2002.
- Viculis, L. M., Mack, J. J., Kaner, R. B., *Science* **299**, 1361 (2003).
- CRC Handbook of Physics and Chemistry*, 80th ed. (Ed. D. R. Lide); online at <http://www.crcpress.com>
- Kracke, B., Damaschke, B., *App. Phys. Lett.* **77**, 361 (2000).